

HISTORY OF THE STATE OF THE KHWARAZMSHAH

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Introduction: During the 11th century and the first half of the 12th century, Khwarazm was part of the Seljuq state (founded in the 11th century in the ruins of the Ghaznavid state). The rise of khwarazm in the 11th century is inextricably linked with the politics of the khwarazmshahs of the Turkic dynasty. This dynasty was founded by anushtegin, the founder of the saljuq Emir. The Sultan was the captain of the court of bathers of Anushtegin Garchoi Malikshoh (1072-1092). of high rank at his court. The court he presided over was also charged with the administration of Khwarazm. In 1077, Malikshoh appoints Anushtegin Garchoi as Viceroy of Khwarezm, and the rule of the Anushtegin dynasty begins in Khwarezm.

The anushtegins were from the Turkic dynasty, and at the time, the three great dynasties that dominated Asia: the Anushtegins, the Saljuqians, and the Ghaznavids descended from one base. On the death of Anushtegin in 1097, Ekinji ibn Qorachar was appointed viceroy of Khwarezm. However he was removed from the noiblik that year and replaced by Anushtegin's son Qutbiddin Muhammad (1097-1127). Although he restored the title of " Khwarazmshah " and was ennobled by that name, he remained a loyal Viceroy of the Seljuqs.

The grandson of anushtegin, a restored khoramshah official, worked diligently towards the independence of horseless Khorezm. Khwarazmshah without a horse (1127-1156). the saljuq Sultan had successfully campaigned against Sanjar. He is a mughambir diplomat and a staunch Sarkar and maintains an independent foreign policy. Chunonchi, he starts a war against the Kipchaks and Turkmens without the permission of his ruler Sanjar. At the beginning of the 12th century, Central Asia is conquered from the East by new conquerors-the karakhitoy. Sultan Sanjar comes to the aid of his close relative Mahmud, the Khan of the karakhanids of Samarkand. The battle against the karakhitoy near Samarkand would end in a complete defeat for Sanjar. Khorezmshah masterfully uses the defeat of the horseless Sanjar to occupy Marv in 1141, and approaches Nishapur in 1142. He died without a horse in 1156 and was survived by his son Elarslon (1156-1172). would continue to strengthen the khwarezmian state by annexing Dixton to the lands surrounding tevarak. Elarslon appoints his son

Sultanshah Mahmud (1172-1193) as heir, but his eldest son Takash does not recognize his brother's authority and begins to fight him. As a result, a fight for the toju-throne begins, which lasts for 21 years, in which Takash wins. His son Tekesh (1172-1200). Captured Nishapur in 1187 and Marv in 1192. In 1194, the Western saljuq Sultan was defeated by qaqshatqich and occupied the entire eastern part of Iran.

In 1195, Tekesh defeated the Abbasid caliph's army and invaded Iraq. Khwarazmshah Tekesh, who has twice expanded the territories of his country and built a powerful state, can be recognized as the most talented ruler of Khwarazm. One of the disadvantages of his policy was the patronage shown to the Kipchak military aristocracy. Kipchaks Tekesh sought to use his wife's treachery to influence the affairs of the state more. The arbitrary intervention of the Turkic "commanders" in the affairs of the state later contributed to the disintegration of the Khwarezmian state in the time of Tekesh's son Muhammad. Under Alovuddin Muhammad (R.1200-1220), the territory of the country becomes more extensive. In 1210, Movarounnahr was seized from the Karakhitoy. No matter how prosperous the country was during his tenure, the country was inedible. In the Sultan's Palace, internal conflicts also escalated, with Turkon Khotun and Kipchaks standing at their head.

The Mongols, who took advantage of such disputes at the Sultan's court, would invade the bulk of the country in 1219-1221. Khwarazmshah Jaloliddin Manguberdi (1220-1231 CE.) For 11 years in the territories of India, Iran and Azerbaijan waging a mercenary struggle against the Mongols. After the death of Jaloliddin Manguberdi in Azerbaijan in August 1231, the reign of the anushtegin dynasty ended in 154. . Khwarazmshahs from the anushtegin dynasty (1077-1231):

1. Anushtegin Garchoi 1077-1097.
2. Ekinji ibn Qarachar 1097.
3. Qutbiddin Muhammad 1097-1127.
4. Horse-free 1127-1156.
5. Elarslon 1156-1172.
6. Sultan Mahmud 1172.
7. Takash 1172-1200.
8. Alovuddin Muhammad 1200-1220.
9. Jalaliddin Manguberdi 1220-1231.

Later, the khwarezmshah davlati defeated the Seljuk and Ghurid States, becoming the most powerful in Persian soils and with huge borders. Even the Abbasids began to threaten the caliphate. According to sources, at the beginning of the 13th century, the Khwarezmshah state was considered the most powerful state in the Islamic world. It is estimated that the territory of the State stretched from 2.3 million square kilometers to 3.6 million square kilometers, allowing this huge border state to form as a great empire in history. Formed by taking the

template from the Seljuks, this state was administered by a huge military unit composed mainly of Kipchak Turks.

Conclusion: In the science of Oriental Studies on the Khorezmshahs state, where Mukhim took the place in the development of Uzbek statehood, research was carried out by many historical scientists. In particular, the rise of the Khwarezmshahs and the further fate of this state V.V.Bartolding "in the time of the Mughal conquerors of Turistan", S.P.In Tolstoy's scientific studies" in search of the culture of Kadigi Khwarazm", atokli adib V.Khwarazmshahs from Yan's historical novel " Genghis Khan a lot of information can be obtained about the fate of his state.

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